

Table 2. Effect of seed treatment on crop stand of rice varieties (>14 DAS) sown in standing water.^a Cuttack, India, 1987 dry season.

Treatment	Seedling emergence (no./m ²)	Stand establishment (%)	Plant height (cm)	Dry weight/plant (g)
Variety				
Utkal Prabha	206	52	26	26
Kalinga 3	185	46	26	24
Ratna	171	43	25	25
LSD (0.05)	ns		ns	ns
Seed treatment				
Dry seed	144	36	24	18
Seeds soaked 48 h				
0.3% H ₂ O ₂	200	50	27	30
0.1% KMnO ₄	200	50	27	25
Water	205	51	26	26
LSD (0.05)	22		1.5	3

^a400 seeds sown/1-m² plot in 10 cm standing water; water depth 10 ± 2 cm.

rice seedlings increases greatly 2-3 d after germination.

Among the varieties tested, Sabita

showed comparatively higher emergence, followed by FR13A and

Utkal Prabha. □

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Response of direct-sown rice to *Azospirillum lipoferum*

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We tested the effect of *A. lipoferum* on direct-sown rice during the Sep-Jan 1989 wet season.

Peat-based *A. lipoferum* inoculum at 2 kg/ha was mixed with 100 kg of IR20 seeds, using rice gruel water as sticker. The mixture was dried in the shade for 20 min, then sown. Peat-based inoculum at 4 kg/ha was mixed with 15 kg well-powdered farmyard

manure, broadcast, and covered with soil.

Four treatments were laid out in a random block design with five replications (see table). Experimental plots of 20 m² received 75 kg N/ha as urea in 3 splits (50% at 30 d after sowing (DAS), 25% at 60 DAS, and 25% at 90 DAS), 37.5 kg P/ha as superphosphate, and 37.5 kg K/ha as muriate of potash, both basal.

A. lipoferum applied through both seed and soil gave the highest grain and straw yields. Root weight, plant height, and productive tillers increased. □

Effect of *A. lipoferum* on direct sown rice. Aduthurai, India, 1989 wet season.

<i>Azospirillum</i> treatment	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Root weight (g/hill)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Seed	69.7	7.7	1.51	2.4	3.2
Soil	67.5	7.6	1.76	2.3	2.8
Seed + soil	73.1	8.8	2.09	3.0	4.0
Control (no treatment)	67.4	7.5	1.45	2.3	2.9
LSD (P = 0.05)	5.5	0.6	0.17	0.53	0.90

Effect of zinc fertilizers on rice grown on Typic Ustochrepts

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We studied the efficiency of ZnSO₄ and Zn-EDTA applied in soil (11.2, 5.6, and 2.8 kg Zn/ha) and as foliar spray (0.02, 0.1, and 0.2% Zn solution) in long-duration PR106 grown on Typic Ustochrepts during 1988 wet season (kharif).

Soil was loamy sand with pH 8.5, electrical conductivity 0.32 dS/m, 0.42% organic C, and 0.50 mg DTPA extractable Zn/kg soil. Urea, diammonium phosphate, and muriate of potash were applied at 120-27-24 kg NPK/ha.

In the soil treatments, Zn was broadcast at transplanting (45-d-old seedlings). In the foliar spray treatments, the first spray was at 4 wk after transplanting and the remaining two at 10-d intervals. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Straw and grain samples were analyzed for Zn content.

Grain yield increased significantly with increasing rates of soil-applied Zn for both sources (see table). Foliar sprays of Zn-EDTA (except at 0.02% solution) and ZnSO₄ significantly

Effect of application methods, rates, and sources of Zn on rice yield and Zn uptake. Ludhiana, India, 1988 wet season.

Zn source	Zn rate	Yield (t/ha)		Zn uptake (g/ha)
		Grain	Straw	
<i>Soil application (kg Zn/ha)</i>				
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	11.2	7.1	15.2	351
	5.6	6.6	14.4	283
	2.8	6.1	12.7	225
Zn-EDTA	11.2	7.6	15.9	378
	5.6	6.9	14.8	304
	2.8	6.3	13.5	240
<i>Foliar application (%)</i>				
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	0.20	6.2	11.8	206
	0.10	5.9	10.1	164
Zn-EDTA	0.10	6.0	10.7	208
	0.02	5.7	8.2	144
Control		5.3	8.2	123
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.5	1.3	43

increased grain yield, but yields were significantly less than with 11.2 kg Zn/ha applied to soil. Soil application of 11.2 kg Zn/ha from Zn-EDTA produced the highest grain yield (7.6 t/ha), followed by 11.2 kg Zn/ha from ZnSO₄ (7.1 t/ha).

The yield response curve indicated that 5.6 kg Zn/ha applied through Zn-EDTA produced as much yield as 11.2 kg Zn/ha applied through ZnSO₄. Straw yield patterns were similar. Zn uptake increased with rates of Zn application from both sources.

These results suggest that to correct Zn deficiency in rice soils, application to the soil is better than foliar application and Zn-EDTA is more efficient than ZnSO₄. □

Disease management

Survey of rice virus carriers among brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* populations in Laguna, Philippines

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We used a light trap at the center of a 1.6-ha rice farm surrounded by coconut fields in Liliw, Laguna, 1985-88 to capture BPH and determine if they carried rice ragged stunt virus (RSV)

and rice grassy stunt virus (GSV).

The 5-m-high light trap was operated every other day. Trapped BPH were individually homogenized with 0.5 ml of 0.02 M phosphate buffer, pH 6.5, containing 0.15 M NaCl, 0.05% Tween 20, and 2% polyvinylpyrrolidone (MWT - 10,000). The homogenate was assayed separately for presence of GSV and RSV by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Numbers of BPH caught fluctuated considerably across the study

period. Peak catches were in Mar-May and Sep-Nov. Few BPH were trapped in Jun-Jul and Dec-Jan, the periods that are the usual start of the rice cropping season.

Monthly light trap data showed an average 0-8% GSV carriers and 0-7% RSV carriers among vectors tested (see figure). RSV carriers occurred in most crop seasons during 1985-88, but GSV carriers occurred in only a few seasons. Disease surveys reported zero to trace GSV and RSV in Laguna and nearby areas. □

Rice GSV and RSV carriers in trapped BPH in Laguna, Philippines, 1985-88.

Timing rice planting to control tungro (RTV) disease

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Green leafhopper (GLH) fluctuation

and RTV incidence were monitored in Lanrang Substation, Sidrap, in 1977-81. GLH density and RTV incidence were high Jan-Mar and Jul-Sep. Fluctuation patterns of GLH population and RTV incidence showed a fairly uniform trend (Fig. 1).

Recommended planting dates were formulated based on these data and rainfall patterns for different areas.

The recommendation was to plant the wet season (WS) crop in Apr-May, at the peak period of rainfall when GLH populations were very low. The dry season (DS) crop was to be planted in Nov-Dec when GLH density also was very low (Fig. 2). Varieties for irrigated and rainfed areas were recommended depending on duration needed.